

Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optical and Radio Converged Architecture in 6G Networks

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Abstract—Dynamic resource allocation algorithms have been used in this paper to allocate the bandwidth and the wavelengths to enhance the efficiency of the bandwidth and wavelength utilization across different types of services in the Time and Wavelength Division Multiplexed Passive Optical Network (TWDM-PON) architecture. To increase the efficiency of the bandwidth allocation, the transmission containers (T-CONTs) are used to carry the available bandwidth in the network to different optical network units (ONUs) that are mapped to three types of services; Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency (URLLC) and Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) which have the following requirements of 1-10 Gbps, few hundred of MBps and few hundreds of Kbps. Therefore through bandwidth and wavelength utilization efficiency, our proposed algorithm ensures the highest efficiency compared with the other two baseline allocation algorithms such as; fixed allocation and random allocation. For evaluation of our work, a simulator has been implemented in Python featuring a 40 Gbps TWDM-PON with four wavelengths at 10 Gbps. Two scenarios were considered with varying numbers of T-CONTs, number of wavelengths, and varying numbers of ONUs. Simulation results have confirmed the high efficiency of allocating these resources to different services.

Index Terms—Workload prediction, .

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, diverse services exist with different requirements, thus it requires a new level of requirements in terms of quality of service (QoS) and the performance of the network, especially in 5G networks and beyond, These heterogeneous services existing in the 5G new radio (NR) need some flexibility to be able multiplexing their communications on a shared channel [1]. Different services in 5G New Radio (NR) will be supported such as enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) and ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) where we must meet the constraints of such services like delay constraints for the URLLC and the huge bandwidth requirements for eMBB respectively [2].

TWDM-PON has been used in many research, and it is a candidate solution to meet the 5G fronthaul network requirements, such as latency requirements for URLLC services which have strict latency constraints by proposing a DWBA algorithm based on reinforcement learning (RL) algorithm and their simulation results show that their algorithm was able to decrease the latency below the 5G threshold [3].

A joint bandwidth and wavelength assignment of ONUs has been implemented in [4] with the help of transmission con-

tainer (T-CONT) traffic. a novel MAC protocol for XGPONs was developed to control the QoS efficiently. By varying their traffic load, the simulation results show that the traffic load is optimally balanced avoiding the congestion between the wavelengths. In another work [5], a combination of two DBA algorithms called a hybrid DBA scheme in the XGS-PON system was proposed to satisfy the strict latency requirement for fronthaul traffic. The experiment results show the enhancement in the performance for the percentage of frame loss when the ONU traffic is increased. The TWDM-PON-based optical network was used in this work [6] to support diverse classes of traffic by introducing DWBA algorithms based on fuzzy logic, taking into account users' priorities to meet the QoS requirements in 5G networks including minimizing active wavelengths while guaranteeing the provision latency. Their simulation results show that their algorithm has approximately 50% savings in the active wavelength while maintaining the latency for 5G traffic below 1 ms. The need for expanding the PON technologies is increasing as the bandwidth demands increase. Thus, an improvement of DBA scheduling using Comprehensive Bandwidth Utilization (CBU) was presented in [7], and results show that the US delay improved for different transmission containers (T-CONTs).

In addition, a recent study [8] considered the study of latency caused by dynamic bandwidth allocation (DBA), by proposing a novel DWBA in 5G NR that involves the wavelength and bandwidth preemption mechanism to minimize the fronthaul latency. A comparison was made to evaluate their algorithm and it was demonstrated that a significant latency reduction was achieved. Many DWBA schemes were proposed to allocate the bandwidth and wavelengths to ONUs, but the challenges are related to the traffic that comes after the cycle is finished, they can not serve this traffic. To solve his problem, reference [9] proposed an LP-DWBA algorithm that predicts future traffic demands and allocates sufficient bandwidth to ONUs in advance. The proposed algorithm effectively reduced the end-to-end delay in TWDM-PON systems.

Beyond 5G and 6G requirements were taken into account to deliver low latency and high throughput for different applications, by introducing a GMA-DBA algorithm [10], and 1 Tbps throughput and a latency below 100 μ s were successfully achieved. Recently, an integer nonlinear programming (INLP) model was formulated to enhance the performance of resource

allocation in the fronthaul area [11]. Furthermore, a heuristic method based on a parallel genetic algorithm (GA) was proposed also to solve this problem. The results show that the number of wavelengths can be saved compared with the traditional genetic algorithm (GA) which makes it suitable for large-scale fronthaul network optimization. Recently, the mobile traffic demand has increased rapidly and it is expected to grow. To meet such these demands, the high throughput is very important to keep up with. The delay performance was their main focus in [12] to reduce it. Thus, a novel mobile-DBA (M-DBA) scheme was proposed considering the architecture of TDM-PON-based Mobile Fronthaul. The proposed scheme successfully reduced the latency by 50 μ s lower than other conventional DBA. It is essential to look for services with huge bandwidth demands for a new generation of passive optical networks (PON). To serve the expected demand, a TWDM-PON solution was considered [13]. To the best of our knowledge, still, there is no work has been done to enhance the efficiency of allocating the resources by considering the problem of mapping T-CONTs and wavelengths efficiently to ONUs based on the service it supports. The key contributions of the paper are listed below:

- Firstly, a new problem definition was proposed in this paper that allocate efficiently the T-CONT and the wavelengths to different ONUs that mapped to three services; eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC respectively.
- Secondly, Not so far, has anyone used branch and bound optimization problem to find the optimal solution for the allocation of bandwidth and wavelengths.
- Lastly, The efficiency of allocating optical resources has significantly enhanced.

The key of our work is to formulate a new ILP problem and propose the use of an optimization algorithm for TWDM-PON architecture, which is the Branch and Bound (BB) algorithm. This BB algorithm can restrict the constraint effectively to satisfy the service demands and enhance the efficiency of resource allocation.

The structure of the paper is organized as follows: firstly, we describe the considered TWDM-PON system model. Secondly, we introduce the research problem and the related constraints stated in Section II; the optimization algorithm is described in Section III. Section IV presents the simulation results. Finally, the paper concludes in Section V with possible future research directions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

A. System model description

In this paper, we illustrate a general optical and radio architecture (ORCA) where the optical and the radio segment are combined. Our proposed system model shown in Figure 1 consists of two main areas to serve the requests, the fronthaul area, and the midhaul area. The system model shows the TWDM-PON where the Optical Line Terminal (OLT) is located in the center office (CO) [3] with the associated Distributed Unit (DU) and Centralized Unit (CU) entities

located between the Optical Network Unit (ONU) / Optical Network Terminal (ONT) and remote radio head (RRH). From the CO, the feeder optical will be connected to the Arrayed Waveguide Gratings (AWG) that have $N \times N$ for inputs and outputs. The output of this AWG will be going to splitters, each splitter goes to the fronthaul and midhaul areas. In the fronthaul area, we will have (n) number of ONUs and then each ONU will connect by optical fiber to the RRH that has a fixed frequency which is (sub-6 GHz) and a connection from these RRHs to the end users by the radio/wireless connection. In the midhaul area, we will have (m) number of ONUs and each ONU will connect by optical fiber to another RRH that has a fixed frequency which is (28 GHz) and will have a radio connection from RRH to end users. for the sick of allocating the resource of bandwidth, different types of Transmission Container (T-CONTs) will be used in the proposed system model.

Fig. 1: ORCA General Architecture.

In the present paper, our main focus regarding resource scheduling is the optical resource, particularly the part between the OLT and the ONUs that deals with the optical segment to serve different user requirements. A simplification of the system model is illustrated in Figure 2 to highlight our main work and the key contribution. The model shows several ONUs based on the related service, where the services are mapped to ONUs in a cycleway to achieve fairness. The OLT will be assigning the considered resources (i.e., bandwidth and wavelengths) to the ONUs based on the service demands. To improve bandwidth utilization in our work, five types of transmission containers (T-CONTs) were considered in this work to carry traffic flows/bandwidth to the ONUs. In this work, three types of services were considered to be served, and the available bandwidth in the system is 40 Gbps. For the wavelength assignment, four wavelengths were considered to be allocated to end users, each with 10 Gbps.

Fig. 2: Simplified model of the considered TWDM-PON architecture.

B. Problem definition

In this framework, we aim to serve both bandwidth-hungry (eMBB), ultra-low latency (URLLC) users and (mMTC) users. To optimize the allocation of resources including the bandwidth and wavelength, an integer linear programming problem (ILP) has been formulated to address the allocation process of the T-CONTs and wavelengths efficiently.

III. ILP FORMULATION

In this section, will be shown the problem definition and the related constraints for the bandwidth allocation and the wavelength allocation respectively.

- Input: Number of ONUs, demands of the services mapped to the ONUs, number of available T-CONTs, and number of available wavelengths.
- Objective: Assign bandwidth and wavelength dynamically based on service demands.
- Output: Enhance/maximize overall resource utilization.

A. Bandwidth Allocation:

The scheduling optimization problem is considered to maximize the efficiency of allocating the available bandwidth within the different considered T-CONTs across all ONUs in the network under some constraints that need to be satisfied as well.

Furthermore, we denote by x_{ij} to the selection process where i is for the selected ONU and j for the selected T-CONT. N denotes the number of ONUs and i, j denote the identifier. The formal problem formulation for the bandwidth assignment is given as:

$$\max Z = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M x_{ij} b_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Subjected to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^M x_{ij} \geq 1; \quad ; \quad \forall i \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M x_{ij} b_{ij} \leq BW_{total} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M x_{ij} b_{ij} \leq demands_i \quad \forall i \quad (4)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (5)$$

The objective function in (1) is related to maximizing the available bandwidth utilization efficiency by dynamically selecting the ONU that requests for demands to be served by the selected T-CONT. Constraint (2) is for the T-CONT assignment, where one or more T-CONT can be allocated to each ONU to satisfy the corresponding demands, this means that each ONU will be served. To limit the output of the allocated bandwidth, we introduce the capacity constraint (3) to make sure that the total allocated bandwidth from all T-CONTs does not exceed the available system bandwidth. the constraint (4) to ensure the demands satisfaction of all ONUs, in some cases, this becomes more stringent and it might be impossible to fully satisfy all demands in the case where the load is very high or the demands exceed the total available bandwidth in the network. In this sense, we assumed that to total allocated bandwidth can be equally or less than the demands of different ONUs. Finally, to restrict the decision variable to be only integer 0 or 1, we demonstrate the integer constraint (5).

For a better understanding of the parameters used in the problem definition, Table. I show the key notations and their descriptions.

Variables	Definition
x_{ij}	Indicates whether $T - CONT_j$ is assigned to ONU_i
b_{ij}	Bandwidth allocated by $T - CONT_j$ to the ONU_i
BW_{total}	The maximum bandwidth available in the network
M	Total Number of T-CONTs
N	Total Number of ONUs

TABLE I: Table for notations

B. Wavelength Allocation:

Regarding the wavelength allocation, the problem definition will make sure to increase the efficiency of allocating the available wavelength in an efficient way based on the service demands. As mentioned previously, four wavelengths will be considered as K . The objective function in this case is to maximize the efficiency of utilizing these wavelengths by allocating them properly to the ONUs. We denote by y_{ik} to the selection process for $wavelength_k$ and the selected ONU_i to be served. The formal problem formulation for the wavelength assignment is given as:

$$\max Z^1 = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^N y_{ik} c_{ik} \quad (6)$$

Subjected to:

$$\sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik} \geq 1; \quad ; \quad \forall i \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik} c_{ik} \leq C_{total} \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik} c_{ik} \leq \text{demands}_i \quad \forall i \quad (9)$$

$$y_{ik} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (10)$$

The objective function in (6) is related to maximizing the available wavelength utilization efficiency by dynamically selecting the ONU that requests for demands to be served by the selected wavelength. The constraint (2) is for allocation of wavelengths: one or more wavelengths can be assigned to each ONU. The Capacity constraint (3) was held to make sure that the total assigned capacity within all wavelengths across all ONUs does not exceed the total available capacity of all wavelengths. Constraint (4) is demand satisfaction where all demands of ONUs should be satisfied if the demands do not exceed the available capacity for all wavelengths. Finally, constraint (5) is the integer constraint since we assumed that the decision variable is an integer value between [0-1].

The key notations used in problem formation are summarized in Table. II.

Variables	Definition
y_{ik}	Indicates whether $wavelength_k$ is assigned to ONU_i
c_{ik}	Capacity of each wavelength
C_{total}	The maximum capacity across all wavelengths
K	Total number of wavelengths
N	Total number of ONUs

TABLE II: Table for notations

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

This paper presents a resource allocation process in the form of a branch and bound algorithm that optimizes the allocation at a specific point in time [14]. The algorithm allows to allocate the resources for the services on demand. Thus, it proposes an optimization search scheme to solve the ILP problem, and this algorithm is called the Branch and Bound algorithm. The proposed scheme aimed to find the optimal solution for our problem that will enhance the resource allocation efficiency by iterating through all possible combinations of the existing decision variables and discovering the entire search space. The algorithm has several steps before finding the optimal solution, starting with the initialization, branching, bounding, pruning, and finding the optimal solution. The idea of this algorithm is mainly to divide the problem into subproblems and start branching with the number of existing decision variables. In the meantime, it eliminates the parts/nodes in the search space when it violates the constraints. This global optimization approach branch and bound (BB) algorithm is suitable to solve this large-scale optimization problem. The main challenge in this choice is the time taken by the algorithm to find the optimal solution since it searches the entire space with all possible/candidate solutions, and with the increasing of decision variables, more time will be taken to evaluate the best candidate/solution. Typically, we can see the branch-and-bound algorithm as a tree search; at each node of this tree, the algorithm will calculate the objective function for this particular case by setting one of the decision variables.

Suppose that each variable is only 0-1 valued. At each node, the algorithm should decide whether or not $x=0$ or $x=1$ is the right choice.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The numerical simulation of the proposed model based on the Branch and Bound algorithm is performed according to the efficiency performance of resource allocation. For the sake of comparison, We implement other basic algorithms, such as the random and the fixed allocation of the optical resources [15], where, in the case of the random allocation, the type of T-CONT and the amount of bandwidth within this selected T-CONT will be allocated randomly. In the case of fixed allocation, the chosen type T-CONT is done manually (fixed way). Lastly, we compare the results in terms of the efficiency of bandwidth and wavelength utilization.

The results show that our algorithm has the highest efficiency in terms of bandwidth and wavelength among the random and fixed allocations while satisfying the demands of services as much as possible. The efficiency of resource allocation was held in two different scenarios; the first one with varying numbers of ONUs, the second one with varying numbers of T-CONTs and the number of wavelengths respectively.

A. Bandwidth utilization performance

Bandwidth utilization efficiency is a crucial aspect in the evaluation of network performance and efficiency in telecommunication systems like TWDM-PON. Efficient bandwidth utilization ensures that available network resources, such as bandwidth are allocated optimally to meet the demands of various services and users. Fig.3 shows the bandwidth utilization efficiency for B&B, fixed, and randomly algorithms respectively with increasing the number of ONUs.

Fig. 3: Bandwidth utilization efficiency Vs. Number of ONUs.

Using the simulation environment with many ONUs up to 16 and five types of T-CONTs, with demands of eMBB service 1 Gbps, URLLC service 400 Mbps, and mMTC service 200 Kbps, we see that the proposed B&B schemes have higher bandwidth efficiency compared with the traditional approach (fixed and random allocation), and its reach to 80%

of efficiency based on the current traffic demands of the services. This is because our algorithm performance increases when the ONUs/load increases, this is because the network has sufficient available bandwidth to accommodate the increased demands, so the efficiency of bandwidth utilization has increased. and this occurs because the network can fully utilize its resources to satisfy the higher demands without experiencing congestion or resource exhaustion, The fixed algorithm follows a predetermined allocation strategy, which may lead to suboptimal bandwidth utilization, especially if demands vary significantly. The random algorithm provides less efficiency by allocating this bandwidth to satisfy the needs. By comparing the bandwidth utilization efficiencies achieved by each algorithm for different numbers of ONUs, we can observe how their behaviors change with varying network sizes(load) and demands. Typically, the proposed algorithm should outperform the fixed and random algorithms in terms of efficiency, especially as the network complexity increases.

Fig. 4: Bandwidth utilization efficiency at different number of T-CONTs.

Fig.4 shows the bandwidth utilization efficiency using a different number of available T-CONTs. In our work, five T-CONT profiles have been used to allocate dynamically the bandwidth to 64 ONUs in this scenario. The behavior of the proposed algorithm shows an increment in efficiency with allocating more T-CONTs to satisfy the demands, the algorithm achieves high efficiency in the bandwidth allocation, and by using fewer T-CONTs we can achieve high efficiency that satisfies the needs of services. In the case of fixed allocation, it has less efficiency than the proposed B&B scheme, the efficiency increases with more T-CONTs, at some point, we may see a decrease in the efficiency even if the number of T-CONTs increases, this is because the selected T-CONT is fixed and it may use same T-CONT to allocate the bandwidth and the available bandwidth will be divided by those ONUs. Finally, random allocation is less efficient in allocating the capacity of wavelengths and its behavior is variable and inefficient utilization due to its random nature.

B. Wavelength utilization performance

Regarding optical resources, wavelength utilization efficiency is a key metric in evaluating and optimizing wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) systems like TWDM-PON. Efficient wavelength utilization ensures that the available optical spectrum is allocated optimally among different channels or wavelengths in the TWDM system. By maximizing the utilization of each wavelength, the system can accommodate a larger number of users and services while minimizing spectral wastage.

Fig. 5: Wavelength utilization efficiency Vs. Number of ONUs.

Fig.5 shows the wavelength utilization efficiency with varying the number of ONUs. With the same simulation environment of Fig.3, Fig.5 shows the wavelength utilization efficiency with varying ONUs. As the number of ONUs increases, the algorithm tries to find an optimal solution by exploring different combinations of T-CONTs for each ONU. Unlike the fixed allocation algorithm where the efficiency decreases when the load is higher, this algorithm may face challenges in efficiently utilizing the available bandwidth, if the fixed allocation scheme does not adequately distribute the bandwidth, the efficiency of this algorithm may decrease as the number of ONUs increases. In contrast, the efficiency of the random algorithm may vary widely and is generally expected to be lower than the branch and bound algorithm.

Fig.6 shows the wavelength utilization efficiency with varying numbers of wavelengths. The objective here is to show the performance of the proposed algorithm when increasing the number of wavelengths for the number of ONUs equal to 64. It aims to allocate the available wavelengths in an efficient way to the ONUs taking into consideration the demands of the services mapped to the ONUs. Since the demand is high for 64 ONUs, allocating more wavelengths will lead to an increase in the efficiency of wavelength utilization to satisfy the needs without exceeding the total capacity for all wavelengths. As the number of wavelengths increases, it can potentially find better solutions, While in the fixed allocation, the allocation of wavelengths to the services is done based on a predetermined order. Still, the efficiency will increase when providing more wavelengths, but the efficiency is not as high as the proposed algorithm because the efficiency of this

Fig. 6: Bandwidth utilization efficiency at different numbers of wavelengths.

algorithm depends on the fixed assignment strategy and it may lead to underutilization of some wavelengths if the demands are not evenly distributed or if certain wavelengths reach their capacity limits before others. Lastly, For the random assignment, the efficiency increases with 2 wavelengths and more. It may achieve high efficiency if the random assignments happen to distribute the demands evenly across wavelengths and utilize the available capacity effectively.

VI. CONCLUSION

The TWDM-PON has remarkable advantages as the main solution to NG-PON2 [3]. In this article, a new problem formulation for resource scheduling (i.e., bandwidth and wavelengths) has been proposed and formulated as an integer programming problem, which can be solved by the proposed BB algorithm. The proposed algorithm shows significant enhancement for the bandwidth utilization that has been measured for different scenarios. In this paper, we proposed a search algorithm called Branch and Bound for TWDM-PON architecture, to satisfy different requirements of three types of services. The performance of the proposed algorithm was verified through numerical simulations. With our proposed algorithm, the TWDM-PON efficiency in terms of bandwidth utilization and wavelength utilization is higher than other baseline algorithms by 60-70%.

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